

A new smart multifunctional polymer nanocomposites layer for the detection of low velocity impact damage in composite structures

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SUMMARY

A variety of new smart photoluminescent polymer nanocomposites layers were developed to be used for detection of low-velocity impact damage on composite structures. These layers exhibit a unique characteristic of showing specific light emission in the visible range under UV-light excitation that could be used to visualize in a quick and effective manner barely visible impact damage.

Keywords: Nanocomposites, smart layer, Mercaptides, Copper(I) sulfide, Low velocity impact, Fluorescence

Introduction

Unlike metallic and other materials, laminar composites mainly suffer from low impact damage due to a variety of causes (hail stones, tool drop, etc...) that, inevitably, weaken the structure. Impact event can cause different type of damages such as sub-surface delaminations, matrix cracks, fibre debonding or fracture, indentation. Under low velocity impact composite structures can suffer of barely visible impact damage (BVID) on the impacted face. These effects can induce variations in the mechanical properties of such composites structures (the primary effect of a delamination is to change the local value of the bending stiffness and of the transverse-shear stiffness), leading to possible catastrophic failure conditions. Hence a quick detection and evaluation of these types of damage is a major concern for aerospace industries.

For this reason, a number of different non-destructive evaluation techniques (NDT) used for aircraft inspection including acoustic emission (AE), thermography, shearography and ultrasonic inspection, can efficiently detect impact location and characterize existing and emerging defects. These detection methods can be classified in two different approaches known as *active* and *passive techniques*. The first approach is based on searching the defect generated by a probe directly on the specimen surface, while in the *passive technique*, the signals emitted by external or internal sources are measured. However, the weakness of both approaches often depends on the critical access of the NDT techniques to observe the investigated area, particularly when such damages occur in region which are inaccessible to visual inspection. A possible solution

for the low velocity impact detection could be found through a simple and effective *in-situ* chemical approach for the synthesis of photoluminescent nanocomposites, based on metallic/semiconductor Cu₂S nanoparticles insulated into an amorphous polystyrene matrix. In fact, smart layers, whereas a nanoscopic phase is embedded into polymer matrix due to their unique combination of properties, not available in any of the individual constituents, nor in the bulk counterparts, are able to generate complex multifunctionalities with a wide range of technological applications [1-3].

In this terms, the research work conducted in this paper was aimed to investigate the behaviour and report the creation of a new smart polymer nanocomposites layer widespread on the surface of laminated composite plates undergone to low velocity impacts, radiated with ultraviolet light of different wavelength (300 – 400 nm). In this way, the presence of defects as matrix cracks, fibre bridging and delamination was observed by a fluorescence emission extending in the visible spectral region, from 600 up to 800 nm [4,7]. This phenomenon is related to the increase of the band-gap energy value, as a result of the conduction and valence band contraction due to the lower number of atoms present in a nanoscopic phase compared to the bulk [8,9].

The layout of the paper is as follow: the first section describes the synthesis, the morphological-structural characterization by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and X-Ray Powder Diffraction (XRD), and the study of the optical and fluorescence characteristics of Cu₂S nanoparticles embedded in amorphous polystyrene. The second and third sections give the results on the previous analysis and on the impact damage evaluation for different laminated composite plates. Then the final conclusions of the paper are reported.

Experimental methodology

Copper(I) sulfide, Cu₂S, is a semiconductor with interesting fluorescence characteristics that to the best of our knowledge has never been described in the literature. Nanoparticles of Cu₂S dispersed into an optical polystyrene matrix was produced by a chemical technique based on the *in situ* decomposition of a mercaptide precursor (i.e., copper(I) dodecyl-mercaptide, CuSC₁₂H₂₅) dissolved in polymer [10,11].

The copper(I) dodecyl-mercaptide, CuSC₁₂H₂₅, was prepared by adding drop-by-drop an alcoholic solution of dodecanethiol, C₁₂H₂₅SH (Aldrich), to a copper(II) chloride solution, CuCl₂ (Aldrich, 99.9%) in ethanol (99.8%) at room-temperature, under stirring. Stoichiometric amounts of reactants were used. The mercaptide promptly precipitated as a white crystalline powder, which was separated by vacuum-filtration and then washed several times with ethanol. According to the literature [12], this reaction involved two steps: in the first step, the cupric ion was reduced to cuprous ion by thiol; in the second step, the obtained cuprous ion and thiol combine together to generate the mercaptide compound, which is not soluble in ethanol:

In order to prepare mercaptide/polymer blends, a little amount of copper(I) dodecyl-mercaptide was dissolved in chloroform and mixed with a chloroform solution of

amorphous polystyrene ($M=230,000 \text{ gmol}^{-1}$, Aldrich). The obtained system was accurately homogenized with ultrasounds, then cast onto a glass-substrate and dried in air at room temperature. The dried films of Cu(I) dodecyl-mercaptide/polystyrene blend were opalescent and white, these films were converted to the Cu_2S /polystyrene nanocomposite by thermal annealing at ca. 200°C for 15s. During the heat treatment, the films became quite transparent and yellow-brown colored, because of the mercaptide crystals melting and molecular dissolution into the polymer. The mercaptide thermal decomposition led to the formation of copper(I) sulfide nanoparticles, according to the following chemical reaction [12]:

The thermolysis of pure copper(I) dodecyl-mercaptide was studied by Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA, TA INSTRUMENTS 2950) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC, TA INSTRUMENTS 2920). The Cu_2S nanoparticles morphology produced by in situ $\text{CuSC}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$ thermal decomposition was obtained analyzing nanocomposite films by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM, Philips EM208S microscope equipped with a MegaView Room for digital images acquisition, at acceleration voltage of 100kV). The crystalline nature of nanoparticles embedded in polymer was investigated by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD, Rigaku DMAX-IIIC). The optical characteristics of nanocomposite films were obtained by absorption and emission optical spectroscopy, using a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer Lambda-850) and a Fluorescence Spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer-LS55), respectively.

Experimental analysis and results

The Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was carried out by heating the pure copper(I) dodecyl-mercaptide sample from room temperature to 800°C , at $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, under fluxing nitrogen. This TGA showed the formation of copper(I) sulfide at a temperature of ca. 200°C (the residual weight percentage exactly corresponded to the Cu_2S percentage in the mercaptide). The Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) runs were performed from 50°C to 350°C , at $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ rate, under fluxing nitrogen and using sealed aluminum caps. The DSC thermogram showed several endothermic signals that corresponded to: (i) the liquid-crystalline transition (lamellar-columnar) at a temperature of 104°C (onset-point), (ii) the columnar-phase melting at a temperature of ca. 142°C (onset-point), (iii) the mercaptide thermal decomposition at ca. 206°C (onset-point), and (iv) a very broad endothermic peak in the range $190\text{-}260^\circ\text{C}$, probably corresponding to the evaporation of decomposition by-product (i.e., dodecyl-thioether, $\text{S}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25})_2$) [8] (Fig. 1).

The nanocomposite film inner morphology was obtained by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). The micrograph given in Fig. 2 show a contact-free dispersion of spherically shaped copper(I) sulfide nanoparticles. The nanoparticles had a monomodal, symmetric (Gaussian), and quite tight particle size distribution characterized by an average diameter of ca. 4.5nm with a standard deviation of 1.1nm (TEM micrographs were analyzed using the SigmaScan-Pro5 image analysis program).

Figure 1 TGA and DSC thermograms of pure copper(I) dodecyl-mercaptide

Figure 2 TEM-micrograph of Cu_2S nanoparticles embedded in polystyrene .

The nature of the solid phase generated in the polymeric matrix by copper(I) mercaptide thermal decomposition was established by X-Ray Powder Diffraction (XRD) analysis of the nanocomposite films. XRD was performed using CuK_{α} radiation ($\lambda=0.154056nm$). The detection range was $2\theta = 5-80^{\circ}$, with step and scanning rate of 0.02° and $8s/step$, respectively. The film diffraction pattern is given in Fig. 3.

As visible, in addition to the polystyrene diffuse alone extending from $2\theta=15^{\circ}$ to 35° , only a low-intensity broad peak located at $2\theta=46.4^{\circ}$ was clearly visible in the diffractogram. Other signals were of very low intensities, probably because of the low

concentration of the sulfide phase in the polymer matrix and the very small crystallite sizes. In agreement with the JCPDS 84-206 table, this reflection corresponded to the (110) plane of a Cu_2S phase with hexagonal crystal structure [14]. An approximate estimation of the nanoparticles size was achieved by applying the Scherrer's equation to the (110) signal, and an average size value of 12nm resulted. Such crystallite size resulted larger than the average size obtained by TEM investigation (i.e., ca. 4.5nm) because of the XRD implicit overestimation due to the absence of diffraction contribution coming from the smallest crystals.

The optical properties of Cu_2S /polystyrene films were obtained by absorption and emission spectroscopy. The film UV-Vis spectrum is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 3 XRD-diffractogram of Cu_2S /polystyrene nanocomposite film.

Figure 4 UV-Vis spectrum of the Cu_2S /polystyrene nanocomposite film

As visible, the spectrum seems to contain two peaks: one strong at a wavelength of 357nm and another broad and of low intensity at 420nm. The last peak caused the

nanocomposite film yellow coloration. The precursor $\text{CuSCl}_2\text{H}_2\text{S}$ /polystyrene blend was not fluorescent, while the Cu_2S /polystyrene nanocomposite film obtained after thermal annealing resulted quite fluorescent and able to emit an orange-red light by exposure to an UV-lamp ($\lambda_{\text{exc}}=365\text{nm}$, 8W). The nanocomposite film fluorescence characteristics were accurately studied by fluorimetry. The fluorescence spectra are given in Fig. 5, and Fig. 6.

Figure 5 Excitation and emission spectra of the Cu_2S /polystyrene nanocomposite film

Figure 6 Deconvoluted emission spectrum of Cu_2S /polystyrene nanocomposite film (excited at 391 nm)

The excitation spectrum of Cu_2S nanoparticles embedded in polystyrene was characterized by the presence of a large band uniformly extending over the 280-430nm spectral range. In particular, three maxima of similar intensities were visible at 286nm, at 351nm, and 391nm. The emission characteristics of film were studied at each one of these three maxima excitation values. It is noted that exciting the sample with these three lightly different wavelengths, the emission peak position did not change but only differences of intensity were observed. The maximum intensity was obtained by exciting the film at 391nm. In particular, the emission peak, produced by excitation at 391nm, can be convoluted in two signals: the first consisted of a very intensive and tight symmetric emission band with maximum at 642nm, the other was consisting of a broad band of low intensity with a maximum at 697nm (see Fig. 6). According to the peak shape and positions, the first emission band should correspond to the semiconductor nanoparticle band-edge emission, while the second emission band can be attributed to a band-trap emission (i.e., a fluorescence emission generated by defects present on the surface of Cu_2S nanoparticles). The band-gap energy of the copper(I) sulfide was estimated by the wavelength value of the maximum emission peak convoluted which corresponded to the band-edge emission, according to the following relationship: $E_g=hc/\lambda_{\text{em}}$. The Cu_2S band-gap energy value was found to be ca. 1.93eV, which resulted of 0.73eV higher than the value of the bulk-semiconductor, which is 1.2eV [15]. Such effect is related to quantum confinement characterizing the semiconductor phases on a nanometric scale. The observed emission phenomenon is a result of a change in the density of electronic energy levels. In the nanoscale regime, the band-gap of

semiconductor materials is size dependent, allowing size-tunable optical properties [8,9]. Finally, it should be observed that the fluorescence characteristics of the produced nanocomposite films were not stable over the time, but after a few months from preparation, the material undergone a quenching phenomenon, probably caused by the cuprous-sulfide disproportionation to zero-valent copper and cupric-sulfide (i.e., $\text{Cu}_2\text{S} \rightarrow \text{Cu} + \text{CuS}$) [16].

Evaluation of impact damage

The study of the optical properties of the developed composite systems by means of spectrofluorimetric and spectrophotometric analysis showed specific light emission in the visible range under UV-light excitation and absence of plasmon absorption (colorless character) [10,11]. These properties, induced by nanophase quantum size effects, can be finely tuned for specific applications tailoring the nanoparticles composition and size through annealing time and temperature, as well as through the polymer type (which influences the nanoparticles size and shape). The nanocomposites with *Au*, *CdS* and *ZnS* quantum dots (i.e. small nanoparticles with the mean size < 2 nm) exhibit photoluminescent phenomena which generate red, green and blue light emission under UV-radiation, respectively (Fig. 7).

Figure 7 Polymeric nanocomposites, based on ZnS, CdS and Au nanoparticles into amorphous polystyrene, under VISible and UV ($\lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$) radiation exposure

Hence, in order to evaluate the behaviour of the polymer nanocomposites layer under low velocity impacts, several experiment were carried out. Initially, this layer was spread on the front/back face of two different composite structures (carbon fibre and sandwich composite plates), subsequently different loads were applied to introduce an indentation which is representative of BVID, and then the specimen surfaces was radiated with ultraviolet light of different wavelength (300 – 400 nm). The impacted area of this layer was fractured exhibiting different light emission properties of the bulk material (Fig. 8 – 10).

Figure 8 Impact on front surface of carbon fibre composite plate under UV radiation exposure

Figure 9 Impact on back surface of carbon fibre composite plate under UV radiation exposure

Figure 10 (a), (b), (c), (d) Impact on front surface of a sandwich carbon fibre composite plate under UV radiation exposure

As illustrated in Fig. 8 – 9, because of a very low impact in the front surface of the carbon fiber composite plate illuminated by UV light, delamination was generated and the damage reflected on the back surface, since the polymer nanocomposites layer was torn around the delamination area, produced a clearly visible contrast colour nearby the damaged region, representing the flaw (Fig. 9). In Fig. 10 (a) (b) (c) (d), several low velocity impacts were generated in different positions on a sandwich composite plate,

obtaining clearly visible results on the front face showing that this layers could be used for damage identification.

Conclusions

This layer work has shown a nanoscopic Cu₂S phase that can be generated by thermal decomposition of Cu(I) dodecylthiolate molecules dissolved into an amorphous polystyrene matrix. The thioether by-product acts as a strong capping-agent, which protect the nanoparticle and avoid their aggregation and growth. Owing to the very small size, a visible luminescence has been observed for these polymer-embedded semiconductor nanoparticles. Luminescence can be excited by ultraviolet radiation of different wavelengths (300-400nm), producing a strong and broad emission band extending from 600nm to 800nm. The broad emission band can be probably explained on the base of a contribution coming from the band-edge emission, and one coming from the trap-states. A series of experiments based on low velocity impact events were undertaken spreading the polymer nanocomposites layer on the surface of both carbon fibre and sandwich composite plates. The results indicated that the layer torn around the damaged area, produced a visible contrast colour whether irradiated by UV light, representing the flaw. This could be of particular benefit when rapid or not accessible visual inspection is required.

Further work is ongoing to refine and improve the fluorescence phenomenon, which currently is not stable.

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